

The Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Performance of The Nigeria's Agricultural Sector

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Abstract

Since the 1970s, when Nigeria began to explore and export crude oil, the government's attention has been driven away from agricultural activities. Thus, given the limited government finance, Nigeria's agricultural sector relies mainly on private sector funding and foreign corporations' resources. This has made foreign direct investment (FDI) a primary source of financing for agricultural productivity in Nigeria. However, the recent drop in the FDI inflows into Nigeria has generated debates around their consequences. To this end, this study investigates the impact of FDI inflows on the performance of Nigeria's agricultural sector. The performance was considered on three fronts: agricultural output, exports, and employment. The analytical technique was anchored by the vector autoregressive (VAR) model to capture the relationships between the performance variables and the FDI. The lag order of 2 was selected based on the Akaike Information Criterion. Having analyzed the series' descriptive, correlation, and stationarity properties, the VAR estimates revealed that FDI has contributed negatively to agricultural output and employment but positively to agricultural exports in Nigeria. This was interpreted as indicating that the FDI flows majorly to the production of agricultural tradables, i.e., goods that may be exported. Given these findings, it is recommended that the government improve the business climate and ease of doing business to consolidate the export of agricultural produce. Small and medium-scale farmers should also be supported with genuine and supervised government finances to prevent such an approach from dampening agricultural productivity and employment.

Keywords: agricultural performance, output, export, employment, FDI, VAR, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

In the first decade of Nigeria's independence, the agricultural sector was the mainstay of the Nigerian economy (Akinwale et al., 2018). In 1960-1969, the sector contributed about 56% to the gross domestic product (GDP), around 70% to the labour employment, and 65% to the foreign exchange earnings of Nigeria (Akinwale et al., 2018). However, as soon as oil was explored and produced commercially in the early 1970s, agriculture was overtaken by oil as the major economic activity of government attention, resulting in lower agricultural productivity (Edeh et al., 2020). The agricultural performance bounced back in the Nigerian economy, most notably in the period 1991-2011, over which the inflows of foreign direct investment (FDI) were rising steadily – from about \$712.4 million in 1991 to \$8.8 billion in 2011 (World Bank., 2021). However, in the last decade, the performance of agriculture has been subdued as a major driver of the Nigerian economy (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022).

By current standards, the sectoral share of agriculture in Nigeria's GDP is around 25%, agricultural labour employment has stagnated at 40%, and agricultural exports account for less than 1% of the total merchandise Nigerian exports (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). It may be instructive that the current dynamics of agricultural performance correspond with the falling FDI flows into Nigeria – there was a negative net flow of FDI by \$186.8 million in 2022 (Word Bank, 2023). These developments have heralded researchers' interest in investigating the role of FDI inflows on agricultural activities in Nigeria. The suspicion that Nigeria's agricultural sector has relied on FDI may be linked to a 2016

report by the African Development Bank (AfDB), claiming that Africa has 65% unused arable land. However, its governments are looking elsewhere for sustainable development. Since then, the AfDB has been calling on and attracting foreign investors to deploy resources to utilize African arable land properly – Nigeria is no exception. This is because FDI directs resources to the thresholds of efficiency, growth, and prosperity (AfDB, 2016). Given Nigeria's erratic industrial policies, infrastructural deficiency, and unattractive business climate, the news that there is currently a net outflow of FDI away from the country might not be exactly shocking.

However, the consequence of such misplaced economic priority on the performance of the agricultural sector is already manifesting. This should worry the major stakeholders because agriculture remains the major employer of youths and the benchmark for labour productivity among the less-educated Nigerians. The oil sector lags in such performance because it is not only capital-intensive, which employs a tiny fraction of the labour force; it contributes only about 10% to the economic output (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). This implies that the oil sector is not the key custodian of economic activities in the Nigerian economy. The popularity of the oil sector only concerns federal government revenues and foreign exchange earnings. Thus, without generous public finance, the FDI remains the key resource that may develop Nigeria's agricultural sector. The present research, therefore, contributes to the stream of literature on the relationship between the inflows of FDI and the agricultural performance of the Nigerian economy.

A REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

There is mixed evidence in the literature on the impact of FDI flows on agricultural productivity in Nigeria. For example, Ogbanje and Salami (2022) established that the increased FDI is associated with the lower contribution of agriculture to Nigeria's GDP. The authors argued that while FDI is an important source of agricultural finance, the persistent naira depreciation and high inflation rates have been dragging the productivity of the agricultural sector. There is, therefore, a high likelihood that the gains of FDI inflows are eroded by unstable output prices and exchange rates in Nigeria (Ogbanje & Salami, 2022). This finding was obtained having estimated an error correction model (ECM) on the annual time series data on the FDI, agricultural output, exchange rate, and consumer price index. Similarly, Owutuamor and Arene (2018) reported a similar finding in estimating Granger causality from the FDI flows to the performance of Nigeria's agricultural sector.

Noting the role of unfavorable macroeconomic indices, including interest rates, exchange rates, and debt burdens, Owutuamor and Arene (2018) supported the view that Nigerian policymakers do not prioritize macroeconomic policies that may attract and retain FDI to boost agricultural performance in Nigeria. In a related argument, Ajuwon and Ogwumike (2013) connected the limited role of FDI to political instability in Nigeria. They described political instability as an indicator of poor governance, a major driver of FDI flows. Furthermore, there is evidence beyond the Nigerian economy, claiming that a disregard for political stability by host governments does not invite FDI inflows into agriculture. Epaphra and Mwakalasya (2017) stated the existence of a negative link between FDI and agricultural GDP in the Tanzanian economy, Awunyo-Vitor and Sackey (2018) in the Ghanaian economy, and Zandile and Phiri (2019) in the economy of Burkina Faso. The common factors limiting the impact of FDI across these studies are unfavourable macroeconomic parameters and government stance towards the development of agriculture in their respective economies.

In contrast, Edeh et al. (2020) found a positive relationship between FDI and agricultural output. Using a mix of analytical techniques, including fully modified ordinary least squares, autoregressive distributed lag, and dynamic ordinary least squares, the analysis showed that the positive response of agricultural productivity to FDI inflows is strong but slower in the short run than in the long run. The authors suggested that it takes a minimum of three years before the FDI significantly manifests in agricultural activities. However, for the FDI to maximally impact the agricultural sector, there is a need to pursue an expansive deregulation policy in the agricultural industry (Edeh et al., 2020). This will incentivize foreign investors and ensure that the FDI gains are consolidated over the long term.

Taking Edeh et al. (2020) arguments forward, Uteh et al. (2022) related the incidence of food insecurity in Nigeria to inadequate agricultural FDI in food production and supply in Nigeria. This indicates that if the policymakers attract sufficient foreign resources to agriculture, the agricultural supply chain can be bolstered, resulting in improved food security for Nigerians. This result echoed the previous submissions of Edewor et al. (2017). In other African countries, Masipa (2018) found similar positive responsiveness of agricultural performance to the FDI in South Africa, Kassem and Awad (2019) in Egypt, and Emako et al. (2022) in Liberia. Nonetheless, these studies commonly argue for the presence of government efforts in the agricultural industry before the impact of FDI in such industry becomes remarkable.

Regarding the impact of FDI on employment, Osabohien et al. (2020) found that employment generation in the agricultural sector through FDI inflows has not been notable in Nigeria. This is because foreign investors are proponents of mechanized agriculture, which demands less labour. As a result, in the areas of agriculture where FDI exists, employment generation is limited (Osabohien et al., 2020). The authors, therefore, did not express confidence in focusing on the FDI as a medium of employment opportunities for the general Nigerian workers. Earlier, Fofana et al. (2018)

obtained similar results in their analysis of the role of Chinese FDI in affecting employment in West Africa. The authors adopted the Pool Mean Group Model and Panel Granger-causality to prove that the Chinese FDI in West Africa has not been notably linked with employment growth in the sub-region. This was because the Chinese FDI largely flows to the development of agricultural infrastructure, which is paradoxically constructed by the Chinese firms. In the end, the local labour in the recipient countries does not benefit significantly from the arrival of the Chinese FDI (Fofana et al., 2018).

Alugbo et al. (2023) considered the impact of FDI on Nigeria's non-oil exports using a vector autoregression (VAR) analysis. The major non-oil exports featured in the VAR analysis is agricultural exports. The authors argued that the export competitiveness of Nigeria's non-oil commodities (especially agricultural produce) has been heralded by the inward FDI. This is because foreign investors know that Nigeria lacks the infrastructure required to transform its extracted raw materials into tradable finished products. As a result, the carriers of FDI find the business of producing agricultural exports worthwhile (Alugbo et al., 2023). This finding amplified the previous conclusions of Ganasekera et al. (2015) for the African economy in general and Boansi et al. (2014) for the Ghanaian economy in particular.

METHODOLOGY

This study is anchored by the following baseline model:

$$AGP = f(FDI) \quad (1)$$

Where AGP is agricultural performance (the dependent variable), FDI is a foreign direct investment (the independent variable), and f represents functional relationship. Equation 1 specifies that AGP is a function of (or is determined by) FDI. For this study, AGP has three sub-components, namely agricultural output (AGO), agricultural export (AGX), and agricultural employment (AGE). This means there are three dependent variables. Given that the dependent variables influence each other, it implies that the appropriate empirical technique is vector autoregression (VAR), in which the impact of FDI is evaluated on AGO, AGX, and AGE simultaneously. The following VAR model is therefore specified:

$$AGO_t = \gamma_1 + \sum_1^2 \alpha_{11} AGO_{t-p} + \sum_1^2 \alpha_{12} AGX_{t-p} + \sum_1^2 \alpha_{13} AGE_{t-p} + \mu_1 FDI_t + e_{1t} \quad (2)$$

$$AGX_t = \gamma_2 + \sum_1^2 \alpha_{21} AGO_{t-p} + \sum_1^2 \alpha_{22} AGX_{t-p} + \sum_1^2 \alpha_{23} AGE_{t-p} + \mu_2 FDI_t + e_{2t} \quad (3)$$

$$AGE_t = \gamma_3 + \sum_1^2 \alpha_{31} AGO_{t-p} + \sum_1^2 \alpha_{32} AGX_{t-p} + \sum_1^2 \alpha_{33} AGE_{t-p} + \mu_3 FDI_t + e_{3t} \quad (4)$$

Where the variables are as defined above. γ_1 , γ_2 and γ_3 are constant terms while e_1 , e_2 and e_3 are error terms. μ_1 , μ_2 and μ_3 are coefficients of FDI and α_{11} , α_{12} , ... α_{33} are coefficients of the explanatory variables. p is the lag order, and t shows the time series. The justification for this analytical approach hinges on the premise that AGO is a catchall for AGP which determines how much agricultural produce is exported (i.e., AGX) and how many workers are absorbed from the labour market for agricultural purposes (i.e., AGE). The relationship can also run from AGX because higher demand for AGX implies more AGE to increase AGO. Similarly, the relationship can start from AGE – a higher level of AGE leads to higher AGO and AGX. It follows that there is a theoretical baseline that supports the view that the dependent variables are interdependent. The VAR model in equations (2) – (4) was estimated using the Stata software. The selected lag order was 2 – based on the Akaike Information Criterion. Before the VAR estimation, a preliminary analysis was conducted on the properties of the variables. This included the descriptive, correlation, and stationarity analysis. All interpretations of results were done at a 5% level of significance. Data on the variables were obtained from the World Development Indicators of the World Bank, covering the period 1991- 2022. While the independent variable (FDI) is expressed in its nominal values (billions of dollars), the dependent variables are expressed in percentages – AGO and AGX as a % of the GDP and AGE as a % of the labour force.

EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive analysis

Over the sample range, the average contribution of the agricultural sector to Nigeria's GDP is 24.4%. This shows that about one-quarter of the economic activities in Nigeria are traceable to agricultural production. The agricultural output has been relatively stable, given its low standard deviation. However, Nigerian agricultural exports have been remarkably low, sharing only around 1% of the total merchandise exports in the country. This export performance is characterized by high volatilities, as the standard deviation (1.65%) is above the mean value. The employment performance of the agricultural sector is rather robust as the sector accounts for an average of 44% of total employment over the sample period – the standard deviation (6.07%) is low to suggest that labour movements are not described with intense fluctuations. The average FDI is \$ 3.1 billion, but the standard deviation of \$2.6 billion suggests that the net inflows of FDI in Nigeria are prone to large fluctuations. The skewness values show that all the variables have an upward trend except the AGE. This

proposes that there is increasing demotivation among the general Nigerians (especially the youths) who are away from agricultural employment. Table 1 summarizes the descriptive statistics.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of the variables

	AGO	AGX	AGE	FDI
Mean	24.37	0.97	43.80	3.06E+09
Standard Deviation	3.74	1.65	6.07	2.63E+09
Skewness	1.57	2.82	-0.05	0.83

Source: Author's computation

Correlation analysis

The variables on agricultural performance demonstrate relationships that do not strictly follow the theoretical intuitions. For example, one would expect agricultural output to positively correlate with agricultural exports – after all, a part of the produced output is exported. However, the correlation coefficient between AGO and AGX is -0.24. Nevertheless, this finding closely represents the reality of the Nigerian economy, showing a very weak link between agricultural production and exports in Africa's largest economy, where the major source of exports remains oil and gas. This finding can, therefore, shed light on the negative association between FDI and AGO (-0.13). Arguably, Nigeria's agricultural sector is unattractive to foreign real investors, meaning that the FDI inflows hardly penetrate agricultural activities in the country. This partly explains the relationship between FDI and AGE (-0.41). However, it was obtained that FDI and AGX are positively related (0.56). This suggests that an attraction of FDI flows into the agricultural sector can potentially improve the sector's export performance. Lastly, there is a negative relationship between AGE and AGX (-0.13), implying that robust agricultural employment does not translate into the production of tradable output – most farmers in Nigeria cultivate crops for self-employment and self-sustenance. Table 2 reports the correlation coefficients.

Table 2: Correlation analysis among the variables

	AGO	AGX	AGE	FDI
AGO	1.00			
AGX	-0.24	1.00		
AGE	0.41	-0.13	1.00	
FDI	-0.13	0.56	-0.41	1.00

Source: Author's computation

Stationarity analysis

Before estimating the VAR model, there is a need to determine whether the series of variables is stationary. By stationary, we hope to establish whether the series has a constant mean, constant variance, and constant co-variance. When these constancy properties are satisfied, we conclude that the variables are stationary, and reliable coefficients can be obtained. If otherwise, there is a case of spurious regression, which does not guarantee reliable coefficient estimates (Kim & Choi, 2017). To this end, a stationarity test was conducted in this study. This was achieved using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. The ADF specification was with both intercept and trend. Comparing the ADF statistics with their critical values, we gathered that all the series are not stationary at levels but stationary at first differences. Each series is said to be integrated of order 1, that is, I (1), at a 5% level of significance. Table 3 contains the stationarity analysis.

Table 3: ADF stationarity test

	ADF test statistic		Order of integration
	Level	First difference	
AGO	-2.4321	-5.2398	I(1)
AGX	-1.2877	-4.2896	I(1)
AGE	-3.0028	-5.5987	I(1)
FDI	-2.1328	-5.6772	I(1)

ADF critical values at 5%: level: -3.5485; first difference: -3.5530 Source: Author's computation

VAR estimates

As presented in Table 4, the explanatory variables are all autoregressive because their past values (in the previous two years) significantly influence their present values. However, it is noted that while AGO and AGX are fairly inelastic (with coefficient estimates less than 1) in their responses to previous events, AGE is fairly elastic (with coefficient estimates greater than 1). This means the AGE responds speedily to changes in the Nigerian labour market. This may also be explained by the fact that there are many self-employed personnel in Nigeria's agricultural industry. As the variables take explanations from their past values, they also explain each other given the cross estimates among them. For example, a 1% increase in AGO leads to a 0.07% increase in AGX in the previous year and 0.08% in the previous two years. However, a similar increase in AGO resulted in a fall in AGE in the previous year by 0.04% and the previous two years by 0.01%. This finding is somewhat counterintuitive because a rise in agricultural productivity should be informed by a rise in agricultural employment.

Nevertheless, this can be reconciled by the fact that mechanized agriculture tends to be labour-saving. As a result, it may be argued that recent developments in the agricultural industry in Nigeria are fueled by the use of advanced machinery and modern technology. Similarly, past AGX values negatively influence AGE's present values (-0.05% in the previous year and -0.03% in the previous two years). This may follow the reasoning that the production of agricultural products meant for export is capital-intensive, requiring less labour.

Table 4: VAR coefficient estimates

Independent variables	Dependent variables		
	AGO	AGX	AGE
AGO (-1)	0.71**	0.07**	-0.04***
AGO (-2)	0.74*	0.08*	-0.01**
AGX (-1)	0.16**	0.87***	-0.05
AGX (-2)	0.89*	0.38*	-0.03**
AGE (-1)	5.30*	0.73**	1.22*
AGE (-2)	-5.62***	0.72**	1.24
C	10.17**	0.47**	1.76**
FDI	-8.57E-11**	2.42E-10**	-7.73E-11**
R ²	0.734	0.715	0.782
F-stat	8.69**	7.89**	27.44**

* Indicates the coefficient is significant at 1%

** Indicates the coefficient is significant at 5%

*** Indicates the coefficient is significant at 10%

Regarding the impact of FDI on the explanatory variables, it was gathered that an increase in FDI inflow into Nigeria decreases agricultural output. In particular, a rise in net FDI inflow by \$ 1 billion decreases the share of agriculture in the GDP by about 0.08%. This confirms the earlier established correlation analysis, saying that Nigeria's agricultural sector hardly benefits from investment in the real economy by foreign enterprises and corporations. It also explains the negative influence of the FDI on agricultural employment as it is obtained that an elevation of FDI inflow by \$ 1 billion decreases labour employment in the agricultural industry by about 0.07%. Both coefficients are statistically significant at 5%. Both results agree with the studies of Ogbanje & Salami (2022), Owutuamor & Arene (2018), and Osabohien et al. (2020) but are parallel to those of Uteh et al. (2022) and Edeh et al. (2020). On the other hand, an increase in FDI increases the AGX marginally by 0.002%. This last finding has implications for the role of the agriculture sector in Nigeria's foreign sector. At present, it seems like foreign investors are interested in producing tradable agricultural products such as fishery and forestry resources. And noting that the bulk of Nigeria's agricultural exports involve extractive output (raw materials), it follows that the FDI resources have majorly flown into the extractive aspects of the Nigerian agricultural sector. This finding re-establishes the recent submissions of Alugbuo et al. (2023). On the diagnostic checks, the R-squared for each model indicated that the independent variables have strong explanatory power (more than 70%) to exact changes in the dependent variable. And the F-stat suggests that the power is jointly significant at 5%.

CONCLUDING SUMMARY

This study has established that the FDI flows significantly drive the Nigerian economy's agricultural performance. The performance is indicated by the share of agriculture in the economy's GDP, the share of agricultural employment in the economy's labour force, and the share of agricultural exports in the economy's total merchandise exports. This study has

established that the rise and fall in the FDI inflows into Nigeria have not progressively impacted agricultural productivity and employment, but they have demonstrated a positive influence on agricultural exports. Given that Nigeria's agricultural exports are concentrated around extractive output, it, therefore, follows that while the foreign investors may be uninterested in the production of raw materials and staple foods, they are attracted to allocating resources to the production of agricultural tradables which are notably fishery and forestry output in the context of the Nigerian economy. It is therefore recommended that policymakers should uplift the face of the fishery and forestry sub-sector of Nigeria's agricultural industry. This may be achieved by relaxing the institutional bottlenecks in the sub-sector and improving the overall ease of doing business. This will help consolidate the gains of FDI inflows into the sub-sector that produces major export output. Nevertheless, caution should be exercised to ensure that the gains are not wholly repatriated by foreign corporations. There should be policy provisions that may mandate that agricultural productivity and employment benefit significantly from the consolidated agricultural exports brought by the increased FDI inflows. Also, small and medium-scale farmers should be supported with genuine and supervised government finances to prevent such an approach from dampening agricultural productivity and employment.

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